

Internationalization Strategy: The Case Of "PT Kalbe Farma"

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ABSTRACT

Everyone definitely wants the business they build to be able to expand globally. In the business world, expansion is an effort to broaden or enlarge a company's business network, both in terms of production and distribution. By entering the world of international business, companies will gain many positive impacts, such as being able to expand product sales, create human resources who are proficient, skilled and keep up with technological developments, as well as strengthening relations between countries. Globalization has encouraged business opportunities to expand market share internationally This article explains what strategies have been used by PT Kalbe Farma in internationalizing the company. Currently, many companies are competing to expand their business to international markets. PT Kalbe Farma is one of the companies that wants to increase its reach to the international market by using several strategies such as joining ventures and expanding the production chain supply in other countries in order to fulfill the production process in joint venture companies in several countries. This research uses secondary data collection methods using analysis of existing journals. It is hoped that this research will be able to provide new knowledge for readers and be able to be used by business actors in other sectors.

Key words:

Global Strategy, Internasionalization, PT Kalbe Farma

INTRODUCTION

Everyone definitely wants the business they build to be able to expand globally. In the business world, expansion is an effort to broaden or enlarge a company's business network, both in terms of production and distribution. By entering the world of international business, companies will gain many positive impacts, such as being able to expand product sales, create human resources who are proficient, skilled and keep up with technological developments, as well as strengthening relations between countries. Globalization has encouraged business opportunities to expand market share internationally (Ratiah et al., 2021). On the other hand, companies are required to implement the right strategy in order to compete in the local market of the destination country (Nur, 2021). In facing global transformation, companies that want to set foot on the international market must create and demonstrate competitive advantages to defend themselves amidst intense competition (Khairani et al, 2021).

In facing the challenges that arise in international trade activities, companies must implement

international strategies as well. International strategy is a part of strategy that refers to a company's relationships with foreign countries. In addition, experts consider that an international strategy is a comprehensive master plan to determine how a company should implement its mission, achieve its goals, and increase its competitive advantage in the global market (Głodowska et al., 2019). The implementation of an international strategy must be adjusted to the needs and desires, as well as the conditions of the local market being targeted. Apart from choosing a suitable international strategy, how to enter international markets appropriately (mode of entry) is also a crucial decision in carrying out international expansion (Martín et al., 2022). PT Kalabe Farma is one of the companies that is currently aggressively expanding internationally.

Kalbe Farma was founded on 10 September 1966, by 6 brothers, namely Khouw Lip Tjoen, Khouw Lip Hiang, Khouw Lip Swan, Boenjamin Setiawan, Maria Karmila, F. Bing Aryanto. Kalbe Farma has come a long way from its beginnings as a pharmaceutical business managed in the garage of its founder's house in the North Jakarta area. During Kalbe's more than 40 year history, business development has been intensively carried out through strategic acquisitions of other pharmaceutical companies, building superior product brands and reaching international markets. Since 2013 PT Kalbe has started planning its desire to become a successful company in the national and international markets. Of course, in the process of achieving this goal, there are many things that must be prepared and done to achieve success in the global market.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Global Strategies

With the growth and development of various companies equipped with advances in information technology, strategy is a very important need to run companies in facing both internal and external challenges. Jain (1990) said that every organization needs a strategy when facing the following situations: (1). Limited resources. (2). There is uncertainty regarding the strength of the organization's competitiveness. (3). Commitment to resources cannot be changed. (4). Decisions must be coordinated between departments at all times. (5). There is uncertainty regarding initiative control.

Global strategy is a form of multinational enterprise (MNE) strategy that treats countries around the world as a global market (Levitt and Yip in Peng and Miles, 2009). Other MNE strategies are usually known as international (export-driven), multidomestic and transnational (Barlett and Ghoshal in Peng and Miles, 2009). There are many reasons why a domestic business operation decides to expand internationally. Here are the reasons:

- Reducing Costs
- Improving the Supply Chain
- Provide Better Goods and Services
- Getting New Markets
- Learn To Improve Operations
- Acquire and Retain Global Talent

When companies understand existing problems, they evaluate their internal strengths and weaknesses, as well as existing opportunities and threats. Known as SWOT analysis” (1). Identify critical success factors (CSF) (2). Building and filling the organization (30). Integrate operations management with other activities. In global operations strategy, what needs to be considered is that we must understand the global view of operations, develop missions and strategies, make the right operational decisions, and we must be able to implement strategies in operations management.

Internasinalization

Expansion

Expansion is a business expansion that can be done by increasing factory capacity, adding production units, adding new divisions, and can also be done with existing businesses (merger and consolidation) or buying existing companies (acquisition). Expansion is divided into two types, namely internal expansion and external expansion. Internal expansion occurs when divisions within a company grow normally through capital budgeting, for example through increasing factory capacity, adding production units and new divisions. External expansion can be carried out by merging businesses or taking over businesses (Husnan and Pujiastuti, 2012; 395).

Joint Venture

Joint venture is a form of cooperation between foreign capital and national capital. This collaboration does not form a new legal entity so this collaboration is contractual in nature. The nature of this collaboration is not merely to seek profit but also to provide work experience for national parties (R.T. Sutantya R. Hadikusuma; 1966, 204). A joint venture is any joint venture between Indonesian capital and foreign capital, whether it is a joint venture between private and private, government and private, or government and government.

Promotion Strategy

Promotional strategy activities are activities to attract a product or service by carrying out concrete actions carried out by the company. Promotional strategies also aim to influence, invite consumers to buy the product. according to Moekijat (2000:443) Promotion Strategy is a company's activities to encourage sales by directing convincing communications to buyers.

International Distribution

The international distribution strategy is the delivery of raw materials, semi-finished products and/or finished products between producing countries and consuming countries. This strategy is used mainly by international type companies that only export. Overseas distribution strategy can mean that the length, margin, efficiency, effectiveness of distribution channels and the role played by the company differ from country to country. This strategy is mainly used by multinational type companies. A global distribution strategy is sourcing, inventory, and local channel decisions into a controlled global distribution system. This strategy is used by global companies. (Dorothy R.H. Pandjaitan. 2015).

Discussion

The History of Kalbe Farma

Kalbe Farma was founded on 10 September 1966, by 6 brothers, namely Khouw Lip Tjoen, Khouw Lip Hiang, Khouw Lip Swan, Boenjamin Setiawan, Maria Karmila, F. Bing Aryanto. Kalbe Farma

has come a long way from its beginnings as a pharmaceutical business managed in the garage of its founder's house in the North Jakarta area. Kalbe has succeeded in promoting its brands as leaders in each therapy category and industrial segment not only in Indonesia but also in various international markets, with health products and medicines that have always been a family mainstay such as Promag, Mixagrip, Woods, Komix , Prenagen and Extra Joss. Furthermore, fostering and developing alliances with international partners has encouraged Kalbe's business development in the international market and participation in sophisticated research and development projects as well as contributing to the latest discoveries in the health and pharmaceutical fields, including stem cell and cancer research.

Currently, Kalbe is one of the largest pharmaceutical companies in Southeast Asia whose shares have been listed on the stock exchange with a market capitalization value of around US 5 billion dollars and sales exceeding 15 trillion rupiah. The current excellent cash position also provides broad flexibility in developing Kalbe's business in the future

Kalbe Farma Internasionalization

Expansion is one way for companies to generate greater profits, by selling more products or services and being able to dominate and influence the market to a higher market and increase consumer interest and greater competitiveness. This expansion is also one way to increase the company's market to the international market. PT Kalbe Farma is the largest pharmaceutical company in Indonesia and is currently starting to enter the international market. This is an interesting thing to study in terms of business strategy and competitive strategy because PT Kalbe Farma Tbk has remained in first position in the last few years in Indonesia. Kalbe has succeeded in promoting its brands as leaders in each therapy category and industrial segment not only in Indonesia but also in various international markets, with health products and medicines that have always been a family mainstay such as Promag, Mixagrip, Woods, Komix , Prenagen and Extra Joss. Furthermore, fostering and developing alliances with international partners has encouraged Kalbe's business development in the international market and participation in sophisticated research and development projects as well as contributing to the latest discoveries in the health and pharmaceutical fields, including stem cell and cancer research.

There are a number of strategies developed by companies to exploit international markets, including:

1. Expanding the market to several countries

PT Kalbe Farma carries out trading based, namely Kalbe appoints local distributors in export destination countries. This collaboration is very simple because it is limited to buying and selling activities only. However, through this network of traders, Kalbe products are available in many countries, such as Pakistan and Iran, even though Kalbe does not yet have distribution partners in these countries (Anggita et al, 2023). Collaborating in the form of a joint venture with global pharmaceutical companies. This step was chosen to prepare itself for global competition. In line with this vision, Kalbe built a partnership with the Hong Kong pharmaceutical company, Innocycle, which later gave birth to Innogene Kalbiotech Pte. Ltd. Through this Singapore-based company, Kalbe, which is listed as the majority shareholder (51%), is not just building strategic alliances. Identify strategies that Kalbe needs to develop now to achieve competitive advantage, namely expanding sales areas, developing product and patent innovations, accelerating the launch of OTC products, developing brand image and developing online marketing for OTC, as well as operational cost efficiency (Anggita et al, 2023).

According to Vidjongtius, the president director of the PT Kalbe Farma group, PT Kaleb Farma said that in 2018 Kalbe Farma expanded its market in neighboring countries. Through its subsidiary Kalbe International Pte. Ltd., this pharmaceutical company formed a joint venture with the Philippine consumer goods distributor Ecosential Food Corp. Establishing a joint venture company called Kalbe Ecosential International Inc. will focus on marketing Kalbe's non-prescription drug products for the Philippine market. Kalbe International currently controls 60% of the shares in the joint venture. The aim of creating this joint company is one of Kalbe Farma's health business development strategies at the international level. Vidjongtius sees great opportunities from international sales. Kalbe Farma targets the export market's contribution to sales to increase from the current 5% to 10% in the next three to four years. Kalbe Farma is also working to develop the Myanmar market. In this country, Kalbe Frama already has a factory and Mixagrip products have become market leaders. Kalbe Farma is also exploring the Middle East market, including South Africa, Nigeria and West Africa.

2. Create an international supply chain

At the end of 2022, Kalbe Farma will also make efforts to streamline the supply chain for raw materials from China. One of Kalbe Farma's subsidiaries, PT Enseval Putera Megatrading Tbk, founded Global Starway Synergy Co. Ltd. i Shenzhen, China. This is done to support production in subsidiaries that have been created in several surrounding countries, such as Kalbe Ecosential International Inc in the Philippines and Myanmar.

3. Create an international marketing strategy

Marketing Based, Kalbe builds representative offices in each destination country based on the results of internal surveys with potential for developing its export products. Currently there are 8 Kalbe representative offices in several countries, such as Malaysia (for the Singapore and Malaysia markets), Myanmar, Cambodia, Vietnam, the Philippines, Sri Lanka and Thailand. In several of these countries, Kalbe places 1-20 employees consisting of Indonesians and local residents recruited by Kalbe. They are tasked with carrying out marketing activities, monitoring the market and conducting surveys. In each representative country, the company also held a number of communication activities, both below the line and above the line. The product advertising campaign materials are tailored to the destination country

CONCLUSION

The research results show that from the results of the analysis Kalbe Farma is really developing its business to international markets. There are several Kalbe Farma strategies that support achieving this goal. PT Kalbe Farma started its international market by exporting products from its subsidiaries engaged in nutrition to neighboring countries. By considering 3 aspects of doing business, Kalbe Farma can become a company that is able to compete in the international market. Kalbe Farma also carries out joint ventures in certain countries such as Myanmar and the Philippines to ensure that Kalbe Farma products can be received by customers in these countries. Not only this, Kalbe Farma is also considering the supply chain in its international market by collaborating with a supplier company from China. In terms of promotion, Kalbe Farma also involves local companies in each country to be key to the promotion of its products. Strategy analysis shows that the current strategy implemented by Kalbe Farma is still in accordance with

the results of identifying business internationalization strategies..

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